

Archiving and Publishing Digital Behavioral Data

Oliver Watteler, Katrin Weller, Jan Schwalbach

IASSIST 2025, Bristol (05 June 2025)

CC-BY 4.0

GESIS & Data Archiving

GESIS Leibniz Institute
for the Social Sciences

- Germany's largest social science data infrastructure.
- Covers the entire life cycle of empirical research.
- Is a data-collecting and data-providing institution.
- Offers a wide range of research-based services for empirical social research.
- Dept. Data Services for the Social Sciences (1/2 of former Data Archive):
 - DSS archives research data and provides it to the social science research community.
- Primary aims of scientific data archiving:
 - Ensure long-term preservation and accessibility
 - Allow for verification and re-analysis of results, reuse in future studies, and protection of scientific knowledge for posterity.

Archiving Digital Behavioral Data

- Digital Behavioral Data (DBD) focus on
 - societally relevant aspects of human and algorithmic behavior and
 - research perspectives derived.
- Concept "digital behavioral data" (DBD) encompasses
 - digital observations of human and algorithmic behavior recorded by
 - online platforms (i.e. Twitter/X) or
 - sensors (i.e. smartphones).
- Overlaps with concepts
 - 'Big data' – often sharing characteristics or
 - 'Digital trace data' – basis for measuring digital behavior.
- Core issue for archiving: how is it collected?
 - Need to understand legal, ethical, technical and organizational issues (i.e. methods and software).
- Focus on two data types as pilot – data collected:
 - from online platforms (social media), and
 - via web tracking browser plugins (data donations).

Work in progress! > Studying cases & learning on the job.

Collecting DBD

Data archiving and sharing > data quality issues:

- intrinsic perspective > technical aspects of the data itself
- extrinsic perspective > importance of how well data meets the needs and expectations of the user

Sen et al. (2021), Total error framework

Collecting DBD – overview challenges

		Selection	Collection	Preparation	Analysis
Online platforms	Scraping API	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal basis and restrictions? • Technical restrictions? • Ethical restriction? • Biases? • Representativeness? 	Scraping tool?	Scripts, programs?	Methods?
Sensors			API configuration?		
Tracing tool (i.e. web browser)			Device and configuration?		
			Tool and configuration?		

- Challenge
- Possible solution
- Solution

Pilot 1: Social Media Data

	Pre-Ingest	Ingest	Storage	Documentation	Access
Legal and ethical issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check legal basis [ToS] • Offer restricted access to protect individuals 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data use agreements (under review) • “Anonymization” (i.e. aggregation)
Technical and organizational issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing of scripts, do-Files etc. possible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upload via secure Cryptshare server (3 Gbyte per package) • Check data at ingest (also matter of staff training) • New file formats 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage space available; BIG data a matter of costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Catalogue entries possible • Standardized metadata for methods and technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Download of non-sensitive data • Access on-site to sensitive data

- Challenge
- Possible solution
- Solution

Pilot 2: Donations of Digital Trace Data

	Pre-Ingest	Ingest	Storage	Documentation	Access
Legal and ethical issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check legal basis • Offer restricted access to protect individuals 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data use agreements (under review)
Technical and organizational issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing of scripts, do-Files etc. possible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upload via secure Cryptshare server (3 Gbyte per package) • Check data at ingest (also matter of staff training) • New file formats 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage space available; BIG data a matter of costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Catalogue entries possible • Standardized metadata for methods and technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Download of non-sensitive data • Access on-site to sensitive data

Principle solutions implemented

- Website for DBD (<https://www.gesis.org/en/institute/about-us/digital-behavioral-data>)
- GESIS Guides to Digital Behavioral Data (DBD) (<https://www.gesis.org/gesis-guides/gesis-guides-to-digital-behavioral-data>)
- Methods Hub (<https://github.com/GESIS-Methods-Hub>)
 - Necessary repository for computational methods
 - Aim: high-quality and easy-to-use computational methods and tutorials
- Data quality app, also for DBD (<https://shiny.gesis.org/dq-framework/>)
- Consulting for DBD data

A lot of learning on the way!

Thank you for your attention

References

- Bleier, A. (2025). What is Computational Reproducibility? (GESIS Guides to Digital Behavioral Data, 2). Cologne: GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.60762/ggdbd25002.1.0>
- Daikeler, J., Fröhling, L., Sen, I., Birkenmaier, L., Gummer, T., Schwalbach, J., Silber, H., Weiß, B., Weller, K., & Lechner, C. (2024). Assessing Data Quality in the Age of Digital Social Research: A Systematic Review. *Social Science Computer Review*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/08944393241245395>
- Indira Sen, Fabian Flöck, Katrin Weller, Bernd Weiß, Claudia Wagner, A Total Error Framework for Digital Traces of Human Behavior on Online Platforms, *Public Opinion Quarterly*, Volume 85, Issue S1, 2021, Pages 399–422, <https://doi.org/10.1093/poq/nfab018>
- Schwalbach, J., & Mauer, R. (2025). Sharing digital trace data: Researchers' challenges and needs. *Big Data & Society*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517251325211> (Original work published 2025)
- Soldner, F. (2024). Overview of Approaches for Collecting Data from Online Platforms (GESIS Guides to Digital Behavioral Data, 8). Cologne: GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.60762/ggdbd24008.1.0>